

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART I. ANOMALOUS SOLUBILITY OF SHELLAC AND OTHER RESINS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS.

BY SANTI RANJAN PALIT.

Influence of water and other polar helpers on the shellac-acetone system has been investigated on a quantitative basis; wide discrepancies among the solubility values as reported by different workers have been attributed to the presence of minute traces of moisture either in solutes or in solvents. Many other solubility peculiarities of resins have also been attributed to same or similar cause.

Solubility of resins, in particular, in different solvents presents some apparently puzzling aspects which have scarcely any analogue in the case of non-resins. Thus we find that (a) when the solution of a resin in an organic solvent, such as shellac in acetone, pontianak or manila copal in alcohol, or the soft resin of shellac in ether, is diluted with the same solvent, turbidity resulting in the precipitation of the resin occurs (*cf.* Coffignier, "Varnishes, Their Chemistry and Manufacture", pp. 43, 47). (b) Secondly, when a given quantity of any solvent has dissolved sufficient quantity of a resin added to it and refuses to dissolve more (*i.e.* apparently saturated), further solution may be effected by addition of more resin. This is generally explained as a colloidal phenomenon according to "Bodenkörperregel" of Wo. Ostwald and Von Buzagh ("Colloid Systems", 1937, p. 251) applicable to colloids. Barry ("Natural Varnish Resins", 1932, p. 18) also refers to such observations and ascribes them to colloidal effects. (c) Thirdly, it has been observed that while it is difficult to prepare a dilute solution (say 5% of shellac in acetone) even by boiling, a concentrated solution (30 or 40%) can be prepared without any difficulty. These types of anomalous solubilities of resins are well known to practical varnish manufacturers, although the real mechanism of these has not yet been clarified. The present investigation is directed to elucidate such behaviours and to offer explanation, if possible.

As to (a) and (c) Tschirch and Stock ("Die Harze", 1932, Band I, pp. 111, 147) remark that "Sehr häufig beobachtet man nämlich bei Harzen die Erscheinung, dass sich des ganze Extrakt Z.B. in wenig Äther löst, dass aber bei Zusatz von mehr Lösungsmittel ein Teil wieder ausfällt, Hat nun der ein Beobachter wenig Äther für den Versuch verwendet, so wird er die Angabe machen: das Harz ist schon in wenig Äther vollständig löslich" hat der andere Beobachter aber von vornherein viel Äther benutzt, so wird er bei dem gleichen Harze die Angabe registrieren: das Harze ist selbst in viel Äther nicht vollständig löslich." They explain this on the

assumption that resins are usually, mixtures of which the insoluble constituents dissolve in a concentrated solution of other soluble resins present. This assumption cannot, however, be generally justified in view of the fact that many highly purified resins, which are known to consist of single molecular species, also exhibit such behaviours and also in view of the observation that the precipitate formed by dilution with the solvent and the residue remaining undissolved, usually contain all the constituents individually. In regard to (c), Drummond (*J. Oil & Col. Chem. Assoc.*, 1925, 8, 64) explains the mutual solubility relationship on consideration of a solution of an organic liquid in the resin. But such a view does not seem to be probable from our general experience in solubility. Mardles (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1933, 42, 135) observed that not only with cellulose acetate but also with resin "a liquid appears to be a better solvent at higher concentrations" and thus supports Livache and McIntosh ("Manufacture of Varnishes", 1911, Vol. III, p. 359) that "a concentrated copal solution is often precipitated by adding more of the solvent." Mardles suggests that under such conditions a portion of the colloid is not actually dissolved but simply remains dispersed in a relatively coarse manner. Garder and Harris (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1934, 6, 400) observe that for resins "the solute constituents have a tendency to carry into solution material which otherwise remains insoluble in a suspended or colloid state".

From thermodynamical considerations it is easy to show that if a solute lowers the vapour pressure of a solvent, dilution of the system by the same solvent cannot lead to the precipitation of the solute. Since it has been observed by the author that in these solutions there is always a lowering of vapour pressure of the solvent (determined by boiling point method in Cottrell's apparatus) it is quite likely that the system considered is not purely a simple two-component system, but there may be complexities present which are responsible for these peculiar behaviours. This idea is corroborated by the fact that the anhydrous resin is not soluble in the pure dry solvent and is only soluble when a small quantity of water is present. The presence of 'polar helpers' necessary for effecting solution has already been observed in many other systems by workers in other fields. Thus, Holmes and Maxson ("Colloid Symposium Monograph", 1928, Vol. V, p. 287) found it necessary to add traces of moisture to dissolve dry sodium stearate and palmitate in hot turpentine, and Faensteiner for barium oleate in a mixture of dry benzene and absolute alcohol (*vide*, Holmes, "Introductory Colloid Chemistry", 1934, p. 100). Even in oil varnishes the addition of a small quantity of hydroxylic compounds has been found to be helpful to prevent gelling, technically known as 'livering' of varnishes.

It has, therefore, been thought desirable to assess the rôle of water and other helpers in such systems in a quantitative way and in the present paper the shellac-acetone system has been used throughout because the anomalous effects described herein are all readily observable and easily reproducible in this single system.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A. Influence of Water on the Shellac-acetone System.

Influence on Solubility.—Dewaxed lemon shellac (20 g.) was treated with 100 c.c. of acetone in stoppered conical flasks and warmed on a water-bath till clear solution was effected. This was then set aside for 24 hours. A jelly-like mass of shellac separated out and the supernatant liquid was decanted through a dry filter paper. 2 C.c. portions of this solution after addition of measured quantities of water from a microburette were treated with dry acetone from a burette until precipitation of shellac just commenced, which could be easily ascertained if the solutions were viewed against a dark background with lateral illumination. Results given in Table I show absence of any precipitation in presence of sufficient concentration of water in the system.

TABLE I.

Volume of shellac solution used = 2 c.c.

Water added (c.c.) ...	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.10
Precipitating vol. of acetone (c.c.) ...	1.7	2.3	3.8	7.9	10.1	10.7	completely miscible	

It is evident that the solubility of shellac in acetone depends largely on the concentration of water. So the solubility of shellac has a meaning only with reference to the concentration of water present in the system.

This aspect of the question was further investigated by determination of the solubility of dry shellac in acetone. As it is difficult to desiccate shellac absolutely free from moisture, the hard resin constituent of shellac was used in such experiments. Dewaxed shellac mixed up with coarse sand was repeatedly extracted with ordinary ether. The soft resin portion, which is soluble in moist ether, was removed by solution and the hard resin left (mixed with sand) was repeatedly washed with anhydrous ether and dried. This was then dissolved in absolute alcohol, precipitated out by dry ether, washed with ether free from alcohol, dried again in a current of warm air. This hard resin (also called pure resin, Reinharz, or α -lac) shows a solubility of

0.71 g./100 g. of acetone when 1 g. of it is boiled with 10 c.c. of acetone and set aside for some time. This insignificant solubility is perhaps due to a trace of moisture still left unremoved in the resin.

Similar phenomenon has also been observed with the soft resin of shellac in ether and also in that of pontianac in alcohol.

Influence on Gel Formation.—20 G. of the same shellac were treated as before, 50 c.c. of acetone were added and the changes towards gel formation observed with addition of increasing amount of water. Results are represented in Table II.

TABLE II.

Shellac used = 20 g. Acetone added = 50 c.c.	
Water added.	Observations.
0.0 c.c.	Swelling of solid with a slightly turbid solution.
0.1	A non-homogeneous gel with solids admixed with a supernatant solution.
0.2	A homogeneous gel with a small quantity of supernatant solution.
0.3	A completely homogeneous non-flowing stiff gel.
0.5	A homogeneous viscid treacle-like liquid.
1.0	A free-flowing slightly viscous solution.
2.0	A free-flowing homogeneous solution.

Table II clearly brings out the effect of water on the process of gel formation and shows that even a slight change in the concentration of moisture may sometimes convert a gel to a free-flowing liquid. (This corresponds to the lightly shaded portion in the three component diagram, *vide infra*). The addition of water obviously reduces the viscosity of the solution.

B. Influence of Various Foreign Substances on Solubility.

It has been observed qualitatively by many workers that water is not the only polar helper and, in fact, any polar compound like alcohol, glycol, etc., functions in a similar way. Hence the influence of all hydroxylic and carboxylic compounds as helpers, as well as of hydrocarbons like benzene, toluene, cyclohexane, has been investigated in a quantitative way. Half a gram of dewaxed shellac (dried in vacuum at 42° and stored in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid) was kept with 10 c.c. of dry acetone in loosely stoppered thick-walled pyrex test-tubes, partly immersed in a thermostat at 50°. This

proportion of shellac to acetone was chosen as the saturated solution had no tendency towards gel formation. Gradually increasing quantities of different liquids (up to 4 c.c. in steps of 0.02 c.c.) were run into the test tubes from a microburette until the shellac completely dissolved and the solution remained clear on cooling to room temperature (27°). Experiments were conducted in duplicate and the results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III.

Substance.	Amount necessary per 10 c.c. acetone.		Substance.	Amount necessary per 10 c.c. acetone.	
	G.	G. mol.		G.	G. mol.
1. Water	0.53	0.029	12. Xylene	No action	—
2. Methyl alcohol	1.12	0.035	13. Petroleum ether	Do	—
3. Ethyl alcohol	1.47	0.032	14. Formic acid	0.62	0.014
4. <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	1.27	0.021	15. Acetic acid	2.20	0.030
5. <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	1.68	0.023	16. Propionic acid	2.54	0.034
6. Amyl alcohol	2.36	0.026	17. Lactic acid	0.69	0.0077
7. Benzyl alcohol	1.69	0.015	18. Diethyl ether	No action	—
8. Glycol	0.903	0.014	19. Chloroform	Do	—
9. Glycerol	Immiscible with acetone	—	20. Carbon tetrachloride	Do	—
		—	21. Cyclohexane	Do	—
10. Benzene	No action	—	22. Methyl ethyl ketone	Do	—
11. Toluene	Do	—	23. Ethyl acetate	Do	—

It should be noted that only polar substances like alcohol, acids, etc., serve as helpers in such solution process but the hydrocarbons, ethers, ketones, etc. are without any effect. It is remarkable that lactic acid, which is both an acid and an alcohol, is the most powerful agent in causing such solutions. In the light of these observations the cause of anomalies among the values of solubility observed by different workers is thus not difficult to foresee. The fact that high molecular weight compounds like resins, nitrocellulose, etc. are sometimes more easily soluble in commercial than in pure solvents can also be easily understood from this.

D I S C U S S I O N .

These observations may be understood in the light of current conceptions regarding solvation of large molecules (Sheppard, Carver and

Houck, "Colloid Symposium Monograph," Vol. V. p. 243; Hildebrand, "Solubility", Chapters IV, V, and VI) which have been successfully applied in a parallel case *viz.* in nitrocellulose which dissolves in a mixture of alcohol and ether but in none of the solvents singly.

There are reasons to believe that large molecules of shellac having their molecular weight 1000 may be composed of heterogeneous groups, some of which being hydrophilic may be insoluble in acetone, while others dissolve in it. Consequently the complete molecule cannot pass into solution as a whole. The presence of hydrophilic groups in shellac is indicated by the supreme difficulty associated with its complete desiccation due obviously to the great tenacity with which it absorbs and retains moisture. These hydrophilic groups adsorb water molecules from moist acetone with the hydroxyl group of water oriented inwards and presenting the hydrogen atom towards the solvent, which can now easily dissolve the whole molecule of shellac. The forces which bring about the adsorption of solvent molecules on the large stout molecules are quasi-chemical or due to residual affinity which is perhaps dynamic in nature, according to Langmuir's idea, as described by Hildebrand ("Solubility", Chap. IV). In fact, the process of peptisation is not limited to giant molecules or micelles of colloidal dimensions, but seems to occur in molecules of all sizes and weights, resins being but cases where the mass of peptised molecules lies between 300 and 1000. In the same extended sense, peptisation is occurring in the solution of soap in turpentine, of calcium acetate in alcohol in presence of traces of water.

On the basis of this picture, the solubility of shellac in different solvents can be understood. The soft resin of shellac, which contains a preponderance of non-polar groups dissolves in solvents like ether, toluene, esters, etc. more easily if these solvents are moist or contain a small quantity of polar liquids like water, alcohols, etc. which confer upon them a slight degree of polarity. The insolubility of hard resins under the same circumstances may be explained as due to its comparatively large size (mol. wt. about 2000) being composed of a variety of groups of different degrees of polarity. The necessarily low concentration of moisture in most non-polar organic solvents explains the preferential solution of the soft resin constituent of shellac in them. It is quite likely that by adjusting the polarity of the solvent like toluene, acetone, etc. by addition of suitable polar compounds as alcohol, water, acetic acid, etc. the soft resin can be easily dissolved out of shellac leaving the hard resin almost unaffected. A combination of two miscible solvents, one polar and the other non-polar, in suitable proportions may also produce an appropriate solvent for hard resin of

shellac, though they may not be solvents when used singly. Such combinations have been realised experimentally, some typical cases being acetone and glycol, methyl acetate and water or glycol, etc.

The swelling of shellac in different non-polar solvents like benzene, ether, etc. is probably due to the solvation of the non-polar part by the solvent. That partial solvation of the resin molecule occurs even with non-solvents, is plainly shown by warming pure shellac resin with dry acetone. The glassy (vitreous) resin swells to a loose, fluffy mass which does not go into solution, but on addition of a few drops of water, swells to a homogeneous gel and quickly dissolves in the solvent.

The significance of such phenomena appears to be far-reaching and throws light on the question of the ultimate molecular structure of resin and the solvation of its atomic groups. The 'blushing' of shellac films and the comparatively low water resistance of ordinary shellac mouldings, for example, may be ascribed to these hydrophilic groups. Judging from this we should naturally expect that combination with a polar substance having less affinity for water will make shellac comparatively resistant to water. Addition of urea has been recommended (Venu-gopalan, Ranganathan and Aldis, *Synthetic and Applied Finishes*, 1934, 3, 167) for non-blushing shellac-spirit varnish which undoubtedly acts by being adsorbed and thus covering the hydrophilic carboxyl groups. Cellulose is perhaps the best to this requirement and in fact it has been observed that mouldings obtained from well dried shellac with cellulose fibre as filler in the form of blotting paper, cotton, paper-pulp etc. are much stronger and more water-resistant. The solubilisation of shellac in drying oil by acetylation or by heating with glycerine in the oil mixture can also be understood from the above discussion. Britton (*J. Oil. Col. Chem. Assoc.*, 1928, 2, 325) observed that on dialysing a rosin oil-varnish through semipermeable septa, the rosin diffuses out but, after some time it separates out of the dialysate. Britton (*loc. cit.*), however, explains it as due to an allotropic transformation of rosin but this can also be explained in the light of our present observations. The solvated resin molecules which first diffuse out into the oil, slowly lose their adsorbed polar groups as the equilibrium is certainly disturbed in the new less polar environment and thus the resin gets finally precipitated.

The dissolution of shellac in acetone is thus a process in which water, though unsuspected, plays a very important rôle and is in fact essential to its solubility. Hence in such cases what we are dealing with is not a two-component system of the solvent and the solute alone but a three-component one, including the traces of water whose rôle cannot be exaggerated,

FIG. 1

Mutual solubility relationship among shellac, acetone and water.

A three-component figure represented on an equilateral triangle has therefore been presented to give a complete picture of the mutual solubility relations, determined for a dry sample of dewaxed lemon shellac at a temperature of 27° (Fig. 1). Compositions corresponding to the blank portion, 'a' show complete solubility, whereas deeply shaded portions are heterogeneous. Lightly shaded portions signify the region of gel formation. From this it will also be observed that to prepare a solution of 2.0 g. of shellac per 100 g. of acetone at room temperature, moisture, more than 200% of the weight of shellac, is necessary, whereas for a 33.3% solution, moisture equivalent to only 3% of the weight of shellac is quite sufficient—a fact which probably explains the anomalies in (a) and (c).

CONCLUSIONS.

The results obtained indicate that the wide discrepancies among the solubility values of resins reported by different workers is primarily due

to the effect of the presence of small quantities of unsuspected impurities, very often traces of moisture, present in the resin in the solvent or in both. The anomalous solubility data obtained by using different quantities of the same resin can also have an explanation on this basis.

Acknowledgements are gratefully made to Dr. H. K. Sen, Director, Indian Lac Research Institute, for all facilities and his kind interest in the work. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. Bhattacharya of London Shellac Research Bureau, Mr. W. E. Wornum of Messers. Mander Bros., Wolverhampton and Dr. S. S. Bhatnagar of Lahore, for helpful reviews and criticisms.

INDIAN LAC RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
NAMEKUM, RANCHI.

Received February 17, 1940.
